

IN THE ENGLISH LINGUOCULTURE THE CONCEPT OF "CHILD" AND THEIR MEANS

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out in line with the cognitive and culturological trends of modern linguoconceptology and is devoted to the analysis of the English concept «child». The object of the study is the concept of «child», verbalized in modern English. The subject of the study is the specificity of the objectification of the concept «child» by multi-level linguistic means. The main purpose of the article is to comprehensively describe the concept of «child» as a linguocultural and cognitive-pragmatic phenomenon relevant to the English national consciousness, by identifying and systematizing the ways of its linguistic representation in the English language picture of the world.

The linguocultural concept is a linguistic unit of collective knowledge, marked by ethnocultural specifics. At the present stage of development of the humanities, the focus of researchers is on the interaction of language, consciousness, thinking and national culture. In this regard, one of the topical areas in the study of language has become linguoculturology, in which language is studied as the most important component of culture, and linguistic unit. The choice for analysis of the concept "child" is due to the fact that it occupies one of the key places in the concept sphere of two or more languages, forming the mentality of native speakers of Russian and English and Uzbek.

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The concept «child» is an important part of the English-language picture of the world and is characterized by high significance in the system of its values, as a result of which it has many incarnations in the language semantics and communicative activity of its speakers. In addition, in modern society, the child and childhood are important psychosocial and cultural phenomena reflected in the culture of the language. The concept «child» is a linguocultural concept, the content of which is a complex system of conceptual features. It belongs to the universal,

correlates at the cognitive level with the phenomenon of the child and childhood in the philosophical, anthropological and socio-cultural aspects, is a significant component of the mental space. At the same time, when comprehending the concept under study by an English national linguistic personality, there is a certain specificity inherent in this linguistic culture, which is reflected in the complex of multi-level means of objectifying the studied meaning in modern English.

The linguocultural concept «child» has a field structure. The core features "face", "not an adult" form the core of the concept under study and reveal its essential properties. They are found in all actualizations of the concept under study. The periphery is made up of the constituents of the interpretive field ("unique", "unreasonable", "immediate"). The social aspects of childhood are closely related to the psychological characteristics of this phenomenon.

The philosophical understanding of the phenomenon of childhood is relevant in the aspect of rethinking cultural processes: childhood and the child are not just determined by the type of culture, but are its real foundation. Awareness of the philosophical foundations of the process of rooting a child in culture opens up new possibilities for considering the concept of «child» in the English language culture. After analyzing the most common features of socialization in a modern English family, K. Hewitt notes that English parents try to integrate the child as much as possible into the everyday life of the family.

Children from an early age are taught to independence, self-discipline and responsibility for their actions. K. Hewitt emphasizes that the fear of "spoiling" a

child is an a priori British pedagogical attitude. There is a prevailing opinion among English parents that the immoderate manifestation of parental love and excessive guardianship harms the child's character [Hewitt, 1994: 48-76]. Americans also encourage independence, independence, discipline in children, but, unlike the British, who are guided by logic and common sense, they are more lenient and tolerant of children's pranks and whims. However, in both American and British society, children are loved. Parents try to make them happy, but they do it in different ways. The British - accustomed to difficulties from childhood, the Americans - constantly reminding that their child is the best. On the example of the «child» concept, we traced the symbolic embodiment of national culture in the lexical, phraseological and paremiological foundations of the English language.

In modern English, the lexeme child has the following meanings:

1. Boy or girl from the time of birth until he or she is an adult, who has not attained maturity or the age of legal majority (a boy or girl in the period from birth (or before birth) until the moment when he becomes physically).
2. A son or daughter of any age; an offspring (a son or daughter of any age, a descendant).
3. A descendant, follower, adherent, or product of (follower, typical representative).
4. A member of a family or tribe; descendant (family or clan member).

The «child» concept includes thematic series - adolescent, baby, boy, girl, infant, juvenile, lad, lass, minor, newborn, offspring, toddler, youngster, youth;

daughter, descendant, heir, issue, offspring, progeny, son [ODS&A: 61].

To verbalize this concept "child", colloquially playful nominations babe, bambino, kid are used. nipper, stripling, tot. A contemptuous attitude is revealed in the synonyms brat, guttersnipe, urchin. 122 nominations were identified, the concept of «child» in English was objectified. A high degree of conceptualization indicates the relevance of the concept «child» for the semantic space of the English linguistic culture. Based on the analysis of linguistic material from various lexicographic sources, we have selected the following parameters, on the basis of which the thematic organization of a class of person names can be built:

- 1) physical features of a person (height, physique, appearance, etc.);
- 2) social maturity (the level of social maturity in relation to oneself - from complete dependence on the outside world, for example, a baby (baby), to the full ability to take care of oneself);
- 3) social characteristics (related to social institutions, for example, a schoolboy (schoolboy), - a legally fixed form of

majority, for example, a minor (juvenile), - social status, for example, a young lady (clamshell), position in the family or belonging to the family, for example, I first-born, foundling)

4) the behavior and abilities of the person being characterized: crybaby, sneak (weeper);

5) expression of the speaker's attitude to the characterized: baby (mite)

The process of formation of the linguocultural space of the concept «child» receives additional coverage as a result of the etymological analysis of the word child and its synonyms that nominate this fragment of reality. The origin of the noun child dates back to 1175. According to etymological dictionaries, it was formed from the Old English 'cild'. The original Old English nominative plural was similar to the singular «child», the appearance of the plural cildru (gen. cildra) is dated to 975. Later (1175) the form 'children' developed. By 1200, the derivative 'childhood' appears [Chamber's Dictionary of Etymology, 165]. As is known, dictionary entries do not provide comprehensive information about the semantic volume of a word.

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